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The Influence of Self Efficacy on Performance with Innovation Work Behavior as an Intervening Variable (Case Study on PT. Indah Kiat Employee)

Tio Teguh Wijayana¹, Meika Kurnia Puji Rahayu², Sri Handari Wahyuningsih³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Correspondence: Tio Teguh Wijayana, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta, Indonesia. E-mail: tioteguhwijayana13@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of self-efficacy on performance with innovation work behavior as intervening variable. The research was conducted by involving employees of PT. Indah Kiat in production division as respondents. A total of 200 employees from 336 total employees in the production division became research respondents, who were selected using a saturated sampling technique (census). Data were collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using the Path Analysis technique (path analysis) with the help of IBM SPSS 24 software. The result shown that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance, innovation work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance, self-efficacy has a negative and insignificant effect on innovation work behavior, and self-efficacy has no significant effect on performance with innovation work behavior as an intervening variable for employees of PT. Indah Kiat.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Innovation Work Behavior, Performance

1. Introduction

Human resources are one of the elements that need attention considered because human resources have an important control on sustainability of a company. Human resources are needed to achieve company goals. If the company wants good performance, then employee performance needs to be managed and improved. Performance is something that a person achieves in carrying out tasks with responsibilities according to the work given (Noviawati, 2016). Performance can be judged by comparing the results of previous work with the results of current work, within a certain period and scope.

To manage and improve employee performance, company needs to take into account the factors that exist in employees, for example self-efficacy and innovation work behavior. Self-efficacy is an individual's belief that he or she is capable of completing a task (Bandura, 1997). Innovation work behavior is the ability to create success with new ideas (Serna et al,2016).

Several researchers (Salman, 2016; Cetin & Uskun, 2018; Nurdin et al., 2020) states that self-efficacy plays an important role in improving employee performance. Rahardja (2017) states that self-efficacy is a behavior that positive for company goals, employees with good self-efficacy will not depend on emotional support, employees with poor self-efficacy will creates the perspective that his work will fail. However, other research (Kaseger, 2013; Noviwati, 2016) refutes the above theory by mentioning that self-efficacy has no significant effect on performance. Therefore, researchers argue that the effect of self-efficacy on performance is not yet clear, shows that there is still a research gap on the effect of self-efficacy on performance.

Previous studies (Hadi et al., 2020; Hadi & Purwati, 2020; Indrajita et al., 2021; Purwanto et al., 2020; Berisha et al., 2020) showed that innovation work behavior affects performance. The results of these studies are contrary to previous research conducted by Cantner and Joel (2007) and Zhang et al. (2018) where it is stated that innovation work behavior has a negative effect on performance. Once again, the authors found a research gap, namely the influence of innovation work behavior on employee performance is not convincing.

Even more interesting, self-efficacy and innovation work behavior not only be a predictor of employee performance. The two variables also turned out to have a causal relationship. Desiana (2019), Berliana & Arsanti (2018), and Nurmala & Widyasari (2021) show that self-efficacy is a predictor of innovation work behavior. In this case, self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on innovation work behavior.

There are 2 research gaps, namely the relationship between self-efficacy and performance is unclear, the relationship between innovation work behavior and performance is unclear, and coupled with a causal relationship between self-efficacy and work behavior indicates a research problem, namely whether the influence of self-efficacy on performance is mediated by innovation work behavior. Literature does not report the mediating role of innovation work behavior on the effect of self-efficacy on performance. The author found little evidence of the relationship, for example in Desiana's research (2019).

Based on the description of the background above, the author conducted research with the title: "The Influence of Self Efficacy on Employee Performance with Innovation Work Behavior as an Intervening Variable."

In this study the researchers proposed 4 hypotheses:

H1: Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance

H2: Innovation work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance

H3: Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on innovation work behavior

H4: Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance with innovation work behavior as an intervening variable

2. Research Method

The research approach used is a quantitative research, as for the object in this study is PT. Indah Kiat Pulp and Paper Production Division with the subject of PT. Indah Kiat Production Division employees. Data in this study is primary data with data collection techniques using a questionnaire distributed offline. The population is employees of PT. Indah Kiat Production Division and sampling technique using saturated sampling (census).

3. Research Result and Discussion

3.1. Instrument Quality Test

3.1.1. Validity Test

Table 1: Validity Test Result

Variable	Question Item	R Count	Sig	Description
Self-efficacy	I am able to analyze long term problems to determine a solution	0.567	0.000	Valid
	I am able to represent my work area in meeting with manager	0.546	0.000	Valid
	I am capable to contribute to the discussion about organizational strategy	0.605	0.000	Valid
	I am able to help set targets/goals in my work area	0.564	0.000	Valid
	I am capable of contacting people outside organization (ex supplier, customer) to discuss problems	0.556	0.000	Valid
	I am capable to present information to a group of co-workers	0.630	0.000	Valid
Performance	I adequately complete the task assigned	0.584	0.000	Valid
	I fulfill the responsibility as specified in job description	0.591	0.000	Valid
	I do the task accordingly with the expected	0.413	0.000	Valid
	I meet the formal job requirements	0.639	0.000	Valid
	I am involved in activities that will directly affect performance evaluation	0.452	0.000	Valid
	I learned the aspects of the work to be done	0.606	0.000	Valid
	I managed to do important tasks	0.590	0.000	Valid
Innovation Work Behavior	I noticed the other problem in the company that are not part of my daily job	0.536	0.000	Valid
	I often wonder how performance can be improved	0.269	0.000	Valid
	I often look for new methods, technique, or work instrument	0.229	0.000	Valid
	I often come up with solutions to problems that occur in company	0.509	0.000	Valid
	I often find new approaches to carry out the task	0.496	0.000	Valid
	I often push enthusiastic employees for innovative ideas	0.473	0.000	Valid

Variable	Question Item	R Count	Sig	Description
	I often try to convince people to support innovative ideas	0.548	0.000	Valid
	I often introduce innovative ideas into work practice	0.639	0.000	Valid
	I often contribute to implementation of new ideas	0.539	0.000	Valid
	I often try to develop new things	0.590	0.000	Valid

Based on the results of the validity test conducted using SPSS 24, it shows that from the 23 question points from each variable (self-efficacy, performance, and innovation work behavior) provides significant results overall. This is in accordance with the statement which has been seen from all the question points after the validity test is declared valid and feasible to be used as a research instrument because the significance value (sig) is 0.000 which is known to be less than 0.05

3.1.2. Realibility Test

Table 2: Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Self-efficacy	0.602	Reliable
Performance	0.625	Reliable
Innovation work behavior	0.641	Reliable

After testing the reliability using SPSS 24 which includes variables of self-efficacy, performance, innovation work behavior with a total of 23 questions, based on Cronbach's alpha which can be said to be reliable if more than 0.6 so it can be said that the instrument is reliable. Therefore, all statements of each variable in this study can be used as research instruments because all Cronbach's alpha values produce values more than 0.6.

3.1.3. Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Descriptive statistics in a study are important because they show a picture of the research being studied. As well as making it easier to read because it is more detailed and clearer. The following categories of respondent scores that can be further analyzed:

3.1.3.1. Determine class interval

Maximum Score : 5

Minimum Score : 1

Number of classes : 5

$$\text{Interval} = \frac{\text{maximum score} - \text{minimum score}}{\text{number of classes}} = \frac{5-1}{5} = 0.8$$

3.1.3.2 Mean category classification

Table 3: Mean Category Classification

Interval	Description
1.0 – 1.8	Very low
1.8 – 2.6	Low
2.6 – 3.4	Moderate
3.4 – 4.2	High
4.2 – 5.0	Very high

The distribution is done by using a hardcopy questionnaire. These descriptive statistics include the mean, standard deviation, maximum value and minimum value. The table below will describe descriptive statistics on self-efficacy variables:

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Self-efficacy Variable

Statement	Mean	Std deviation
I am able to analyze long term problems to determine a solution	4.50	0.501
I am able to represent my work area in meeting with manager	4.45	0.498
I am capable to contribute to the discussion about organizational strategy	4.54	0.520
I am able to help set targets/goals in my work area	4.63	0.485
I am capable of contacting people outside organization (ex supplier, customer) to discuss problems	4.50	0.511
I am capable to present information to a group of co-workers	4.59	0.514
Total Mean	4.52	

Based on the table above, it can be seen from the descriptive statistics of the respondents in providing an assessment of the self-efficacy variable. For the independent variable, namely self-efficacy, it is known that the total mean is 4.52 where this shows that the self-efficacy of employees at PT. Indah Kiat is included in the very high category.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Performance Variable

Statement	Mean	Std deviation
I adequately complete the task assigned	4.41	0.551
I fulfill the responsibility as specified in job description	4.43	0.516
I do the task accordingly with the expected	4.50	0.521
I meet the formal job requirements	4.50	0.558
I am involved in activities that will directly affect performance evaluation	4.58	0.515
I learned the aspects of the work to be done	4.51	0.521
I managed to do important tasks	4.50	0.540
Total Mean	4.49	

Based on the table above, it can be seen from the descriptive statistics of the respondents in giving an assessment of the performance variable. For the dependent variable, namely performance, it is known that the total mean is 4.49 which in this case indicates that the performance of employees PT. Indah Kiat is included in the very high category.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Innovation Work Behavior Variable

Statement	Mean	Std deviation
I noticed the other problem in the company that are not part of my daily job	3.91	0.791
I often wonder how performance can be improved	4.11	0.629
I often look for new methods, technique, or work instrument	4.16	0.731
I often come up with solutions to problems that occur in company	4.01	0.730
I often find new approach to carry out the task	4.02	0.757
I often push enthusiastic employee for innovative ideas	4.01	0.723
I often try to convince people to support innovative ideas	3.98	0.743
I often introduce innovative ideas into work practice	3.82	0.777
I often contribute to implementation of new ideas	4.01	0.726
I often try to develop new things	4.09	0.721
Total Mean	4.01	

Based on the table above, it can be seen from the descriptive statistics of the respondents in providing an assessment of the innovation work behavior variable. For the independent variable, namely innovation work behavior, it is known that the total mean is 4.01 which shows that the innovation work behavior of PT. Indah Kiat employees are included in the high category.

3.2. Classical Assumption Test

3.2.1 Normality Test

In the normality test, the researcher uses the exact approach where the p-value calculated by the exact approach will produce an accurate p-value. After the normality test using SPSS 24 software, the results obtained from the Exact Sig value (2-tailed) is 0.200 where the value is greater than 0.05. So from these results it can be said that the data in this study are normally distributed.

3.2.2 Multicollinearity Test

Table 7: Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
Self-efficacy	1.000	1.000	no multicollinearity
Innovation Work Behavior	1.000	1.000	no multicollinearity

Based on the multicollinearity test that has been carried out using SPSS 24 software, it shows results that are in accordance with the criteria, namely tolerance for the self-efficacy variable (x) and innovation work behavior (z) is 1,000 which if the tolerance value is > 0.10 then there is no multicollinearity in the regression model, in addition

to the VIF value of 1,000, the value is < 10.00 which means that there is no multicollinearity in the regression model. So it can be seen that the regression model of this study does not occur multicollinearity.

3.2.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test can be done by using the glejser calculation method. The following is a further description in the table:

Table 8: Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Variable	Sig	Description
Self-efficacy	0.901	No heteroscedasticity
Innovation Work Behavior	0.907	No heteroscedasticity

The significance value (sig.) for the independent variable, namely self-efficacy is 0.091 and the variable of innovative work behavior is 0.907. The significance values (sig.) indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity due to the significance value (sig.) of the two independent variables being > 0.05 .

3.3 Data Analysis Result and Hypothesis Test

3.3.1 Hypothesis 1 and 2 Test

Table 9: Multiple Linear Regression Step 1 Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Self-efficacy	0.747	0.063	0.634	11.784	.000
Innovation Work Behavior	0.090	0.031	0.155	2.875	.004
Dependent Variable: Performance					

3.3.1.1 Hypothesis 1

After testing using SPSS 24 software, the results were obtained, where the value of the t-count of self-efficacy is 11.784. The probability value (p) is seen from the sig column obtained is 0.000 which means the value (p) < 0.05 . Based on these results, it can be seen that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 1 self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance is accepted.

3.3.1.2. Hypothesis 2

After testing, the results of the t-count which value is 2.875 and a probability value (p) which can be seen in the column (sig.) is 0.004 means that the value (p) < 0.05 . From these results it can be concluded that innovation work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 2 innovation work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance is accepted.

3.3.2 Hypothesis 3 Test

Table 10: Multiple Linear Regression Step 2 Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Self-efficacy	0.030	0.145	0.015	0.210	0.834
Dependent Variable: Innovation Work Behavior					

Based on the results that have been included in the table above, the results of the t-calculation of self-efficacy are obtained with a value of 0.210 and a probability value (p) that can be seen in the column (sig.) is 0.834 which means that the value is greater than 0.05. From these results it can be seen that self-efficacy has no effect on innovation work behavior because the value (sig.) exceeds the recommended limit. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 3 self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on innovation work behavior is rejected.

3.3.3 Sobel Test

The next step is to test the influence of the intervening variables in hypothesis 4. This step serves to confirm the role that innovation work behavior has as an intervening variable from performance as a dependent variable on self-efficacy and self-efficacy variable as an independent variable. This test is carried out using the Sobel formula in its calculations. The following is a further explanation of the standard error calculation with coefficients with indirect effects:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P3 &= 0.015 & Se3 &= 0.145 \\
 P2 &= 0.155 & Se2 &= 0.031 \\
 Se32 &= \sqrt{(P3^2 \cdot Se2^2) + (P2^2 \cdot Se3^2) + (Se3^2 \cdot Se2^2)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0.015^2 \cdot 0.031^2) + (0.155^2 \cdot 0.145^2) + (0.145^2 \cdot 0.031^2)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0.000225 \cdot 0.000961) + (0.024025 \cdot 0.021025) + (0.021025 \cdot 0.000961)} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0.000000216225) + (0.000505125625) + (0.000020205025)} \\
 &= \sqrt{0.000525546875} = 0.022924809
 \end{aligned}$$

The following is the calculation of the t-test values that have been obtained:

$$t = \frac{P3 \cdot P2}{Se32} = \frac{0.002325}{0.022925} = 0.101418$$

Based on the calculation results, it can be seen that the t value obtained is 0.101418. These results are again compared with the t table that the author has calculated, which is 1.65. Thus, the known t value 0.101418 is smaller than 1.65. From these results, it can be seen that the mediation role has no effect.

It is hereby stated that Hypothesis 4 is rejected. So, it can be concluded that the innovation work behavior variable which is the intervening variable in this study does not have the expected effect on other variables, namely self-efficacy and performance, so it can be seen that self-efficacy can have a direct effect without the need for mediation.

3.3.4 Simultant Test (F test)

Table 11: F Test

Model	F	Sig.
Regression	74.086	0.000
Predictors: Self-efficacy (X) and Innovation Work Behavior (Z)		
Dependent variable: Performance (Y)		

After the F test, it is known that the value (sig.) is 0.000, where the value is < 0.05 . Furthermore, a comparison is made between the calculated F value and the standard F table value. It is known that the calculated F value is 74.086 where the value is greater than the F table value, which is 3.04. So from the results of the F test above, it can be concluded that there is a simultaneous effect on the variables of self-efficacy and innovation work behavior on performance.

3.3.5 Determination Test (R^2)

Table 12: Determination Test

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of Estimate
1	0.655	0.429	0.423	1.568

Based on the results in the table above, it can be seen that self-efficacy and innovation work behavior have a simultaneous influence on performance which can be seen in the Adjusted R Square column which is 0.423. These results mean that 0.423 or (42%) performance is influenced by self-efficacy and innovation work behavior, so that the remaining 58% (100% - 42%) is influenced by various other variables outside this research model.

4 Discussion

4.1 Effect of Self-Efficacy on Performance

At PT. Indah Kiat found that employees have self-efficacy that affects performance. It is proven that based on the results of the linear regression test, a significance value of 0.000 is obtained, which means less than 0.05 and significant. So when employees have high self-efficacy, performance is also high. Vice versa the self-efficacy of low-performance employees is also low.

From the results of descriptive statistics, the self-efficacy has an interpretation rate of 4.59 (very high). This figure indicates that the employee self-efficacy of the production division of PT. Indah Kiat is very high. High self-efficacy is indicated by the ability of employees to contribute to discussions about organizational strategy. If you look at the performance interpretation figure of 4.49 (very high), then the hypothesis is correct that self-efficacy has a positive effect on performance.

Similar research results were found in the results of previous research, from Berliana & Arsanti (2018) that the efficacy has a positive effect on employee performance. Other similar research conducted by Desiana (2019), as well as previous research from Salman et al. (2016) which from several previous journals concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between self-efficacy and performance.

4.2 Effect of Innovation Work Behavior on Performance

Innovation work behavior is the introduction and application of new ideas, processes, products or procedures designed for better performance at work, so with a good innovation work behavior by application of new ideas in solving a problem in production will create or produce better performance.

The results of this study show that the innovation work behavior of employees at PT. Indah Kiat has an effect on performance, so this is indeed in accordance with the results of the hypothesis. It is proven by the significance value of multiple linear regression of 0.004 is more than 0.05. With the large influence of innovation work behavior on performance, it can be interpreted that employees in the company are willing to find new work methods in solving existing problems so that with new solutions it is hoped that they will solve a problem, and be receptive

to innovative ideas in organizational groups, as well as looking for ways to solve problems. improving or developing new things in a job. So that the higher the innovation work behavior carried out by each individual in the organization will create increased performance.

Similar research results were found in previous studies, namely Hsiao et al. (2011). Other previous studies that are able to support this research are Hadi and Purwati (2020) and previous research from Berliana & Arsanti (2018) which from several previous journals concluded that there was a positive and significant influence between innovation work behavior and performance.

4.3 Effect of Self-Efficacy on Innovation Work Behavior

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief that he is able to complete a task, where an individual has a level of confidence that he is capable to take good or bad actions. So the higher the level of self-efficacy, the more an individual believes in his ability to successfully complete something in a difficult situation.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the self-efficacy of employees at PT. Indah Kiat did not have a significant effect on innovation work behavior. The significance value obtained is 0.834 that more than 0.05. Looking at the results of descriptive statistics from self-efficacy which has an interpretation number of 4.59 (very high), while the number from the interpretation of innovation work behavior is 4.01 (high), it can be seen that efficacy has no effect on innovation work behavior. The not high effect of self-efficacy on innovation work behavior because high self-efficacy does not necessarily generate innovation work behavior. For example, employees can ask how to get better performance or look for a good method without having to have high self-efficacy. Innovation work behavior is triggered by things other than self-efficacy that are not included in this research model. These results are in accordance with the journal Wardhani & Gulo (2017).

4.4 Effect of Self-Efficacy on Performance with Innovation Work Behavior as Intervening Variable

Based on the research results, the role of innovation work behavior as an intervening variable is not significant. Intended from the results of the Sobel test calculation where the t value is 0.101418 which is smaller than the calculated t table of 1.65. The results state that the employees of PT. Indah Kiat's production division has self-efficacy which can have a direct impact on performance without an innovation work behavior process.

The employees of PT. Indah Kiat's production division has confidence in completing tasks so that it has good performance without going through innovation work behavior due to standard operating procedures (SOPs) in work routines. In reality employees rarely carry out innovation work behaviors, it can be because of the experience of employees who work still few and still feel inadequate so they can only follow the procedures given by the company. For example, if an issue occurs in the production machine, employees with good work experience are able to solve the problem directly. This has a direct effect on performance without the need to go through an innovation work process because they have become someone who is an expert in their respective fields. So that the performance of the employees of PT. Indah Kiat in the production division is influenced by self-efficacy without the need for innovation behavior as a mediation.

5 Conclusion

The results of the study are described as follows:

1. Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on performance.
2. Innovation work behavior has a positive and significant effect on performance.
3. Self-efficacy has no significant effect on innovation work behavior.
4. Innovation work behavior does not mediate the effect of self-efficacy on performance.

The following suggestions can be given:

1. For Company
 - a. Need to focus on improving the quality of employees by deepening experience because there are still some employees who feel low on experience which will break their confidence to do work. The effort that can be implemented is by seniors share knowledge and experience with juniors in different fields.
 - b. Company should increase the confidence of an individual by conducting regular training according to their field, holding teamwork training which is expected to build synergy between individuals where employees learn to know more about the media and understand more about new information in existing problems on the company.
2. For Further Researchers
 - a. It is recommended to add variables that can affect performance in order to expand the results. For example, the motivation variable as an intervening variable (Noviawati, 2016), or a capability variable (Berliana & Arsanti, 2018).
 - b. Further researchers are also expected to be able to increase the number of respondents and choose different research objects to expand the range of sampling so that research results are even better.

This research still has some limitation such as:

1. There are still few previous studies that have analyzed this research model. This is a limitation but also an advantage. The limitation is that the search for references becomes a little more difficult but still has good quality because the average research of the same type falls into the category of international research.
2. In the preparation of questionnaire questions there are still errors in the innovation work behavior questionnaire where the questionnaire questions should have an impact on the next variable, namely performance. The content on the innovation work behavior question is still an input and not an output that must have an impact on the next variable.
3. The use of questionnaire questions based on a single source which is an individual decision so that there will be potential for bias. In each component of the questionnaire questions, it is better to use multisource where each position has different question variables. It is recommended that the research questions be adapted to the characteristics of the job.

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